

UNDERSTANDING CONSUMER BUYING BEHAVIOR TOWARDS ONLINE FOOD DELIVERY APPS AMONG PRIVATE AND PUBLIC HOSPITAL NURSES IN PAMPANGA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the increasing reliance on online food delivery services among nurses, recognizing that their demanding schedules often make traditional meal sourcing difficult. A descriptive cross-sectional design was used to assess the buying behavior of hospital nurses in relation to socio-economic variables such as age, sex, shift type, education, hospital type, income, and years of service. Data were collected via an adapted questionnaire and analyzed using measures of central tendency and variability. Most respondents were female nurses in early adulthood, college graduates, working morning shifts, earning below ₱35,000, and with more than five years of service. Food Panda and Grab Food were the most used platforms, valued for convenience and speed. Lunch was the most commonly ordered meal, with fast food as the top preference, highlighting a tendency toward quick, affordable options. While most respondents spent less than ₱1,000 weekly, a few showed high dependency on delivery services. Cash on delivery was the main payment method, but a shift toward digital transactions was noted. Convenience, accessibility, and efficiency motivated food delivery app use, while food quality, delivery delays, and cost were major barriers. Promotional offers had minimal influence on decisions. The study highlights the need for practical, time-saving, yet health-conscious food options for nurses. Promoting nutrition awareness and encouraging collaboration between healthcare institutions and food delivery providers could improve access to healthier meals and support nurses' overall wellness.

Keywords: *Consumer Buying Behavior, Online Food Delivery Services, Food Delivery Apps, Online Ordering*

INTRODUCTION

Online delivery platforms dramatic surge accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, Changed Food purchasing behaviors across the world. Millions of users in the Philippines alone have increasingly relied on services like Food Panda and Grab Food because of the quarantine restrictions to obtain meals conveniently (Beyrouthy, 2024; Market Research Philippines, 2023). Understanding of these platforms and how they influence consumer buying behavior of hospital nurses in Pampanga is limited despite its growing popularity. This Services gaining popularity globally has entered the healthcare sector where hospital nurses especially those in Pampanga face distinct challenges related to their demanding work schedules, shift rotations, and limited access to healthy food options within hospital settings (Horton Dias & Dawson, 2020; Monaghan et al., 2018). Consumer buying behaviors that can impact nurses' overall well-being and professional performance can be contributed by those distinct challenges.

Demographic factors, such as age, sex, shift, educational attainment, type of hospital, income and years of service have been identified in existing literature as factors that can influence consumer buying behavior for online food delivery apps (Esguerra et al., 2023; Lee et. al, 2019). For instance, these online food delivery apps are more frequently used by younger adults who are accustomed to using technology. When it comes to sex differences are prominent in categories such as convenience, health cost and speed. Nurses' increasing reliance on food delivery are potentially brought by irregular shifts and workplace constraints, yet only few studies have correlated these behaviors specifically to health outcomes among hospital nurses in the Philippines. While existing literature examined general consumers' use of food delivery apps, existing literature focused on healthcare professionals, nurses in particular are few. Understanding of how occupational demands influence consumer buying behavior is limited because of this gap.

With this gap this study aims to investigate the consumer buying behavior regarding online food delivery apps among private and public hospital nurses in Pampanga. It specifically explores how demographic profiles influence typical consumer buying behavior, motivating factors, and restraining factors in using these apps. The research questions focus on the relationship between hospital nurses' demographic data and their choice of food when purchasing using online platforms. These factors significantly affect nurses' usage patterns stated in the hypothesis. Guiding this research study, the conceptual framework integrates nurses' demographic factors with their consumer buying behaviors, together with motivating factors such as convenience, variety of meals, fast delivery time and restraining factors which includes hygiene and health concerns. To ensure clarity, definitions for key terms such as consumer buying behavior, online food delivery apps, and motivating/restraining factors are defined. The study contributes valuable insights for healthcare professionals, policymakers, restaurants and food delivery companies, by conveying this in the literature. While adapting digital food services and targeting interventions to promote healthier habits among nurses to better meet their unique needs. Improved nurse well-being, work

performance, and patient care outcomes in the region may be fostered by these studies findings.

Following the start of the COVID-19 pandemic people around the world confined at home attributed to the surge in online food delivery. Online food delivery apps became eminent to restaurants and fast-food industry wherein consumer buying behaviors are evident. Acting as a pathway between customers and food establishments, as well as providing a variety of cuisines and distinct meals are what made this platform popular. Encountering distinct challenges while trying to juggle their demanding work schedules with personal responsibilities affects nurses' food choices and overall well-being. With these circumstances this research study aimed to explore various demographic characteristics of both private and public hospital nurses in relation to their typical consumer buying behaviors, motivating and restraining factors which influence their use of online food delivery applications. It specifically sought to determine whether demographic factors such as sex, age, shift type, highest educational attainment, hospital type, monthly income, and years of service, along with typical purchasing behaviors, motivating factors, and restraints, significantly influenced the online food delivery purchasing behavior of hospital nurses.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to identify the consumer buying behavior of hospital nurses in Pampanga regarding the use of online food delivery apps.

Specifically, the researchers aimed to:

1. Identify the demographic characteristics of the respondents, in terms of:
 - a. Age
 - b. Sex
 - c. Type of shift
 - d. Highest Educational Attainment
 - e. Type of Hospital
 - f. Individual Monthly Income
 - g. Years of Service
2. Describe the typical buying behaviors of respondents regarding online food delivery apps.
3. Determine factors related to consumer buying behaviors as to motivation and barriers on the use of online food delivery apps.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative descriptive cross-sectional technique was used, by which data were acquired at one particular time to provide an overall view of nurses' demographic profiles, buying behaviors, and influencing factors such as motivation and barriers. This design

was chosen because it was simple to carry out, relatively inexpensive, and capable of identifying patterns without the need for follow-up, providing initial data that can inform more detailed research in the future.

Respondents and Setting

A purposive sampling technique was employed, through which 186 respondents, with 108 (58.1%) from public hospitals and 78 (41.9%) from private hospitals were chosen from a total of 526 in Pampanga hospitals. Registered nurses, aged 20-59, and users of online food delivery apps were the inclusion criteria of the study. In Central Luzon (Region 3), Pampanga ranked second to Calabarzon in nurse-to-population ratio totaling 7,936 nurses (Balita, 2023). Pampanga was selected as the setting stemming from its prominence among the numerous public and private hospitals in the region.

Research Instrument

Data were gathered using a validated and pilot-tested questionnaire adapted from Arsiwala (2020). Demographics, buying behaviors, and factors as to motivation and barriers were the content of the instrument composed of four sections. Using a 5-point Likert scale, these factors were rated. To ensure accessibility, the questionnaires were disseminated through digital in Google Forms and physical in printed copies.

Section one aimed to gather information on the demographic profile of hospital nurses, specifically focusing on their sex, age, type of shift, highest educational attainment, type of hospital, years of service, and monthly income. Section two addressed questions pertaining to typical buying behaviors related to the use of online food delivery applications. The last two sections utilized a 5-point Likert scale, with 1 representing “strongly disagree” and 5 representing “strongly agree.” These sections included eight statements for motivating factors and five statements for restraining factors.

Pilot testing was conducted to ensure the instrument’s reliability producing values in Cronbach’s α coefficients of 0.869 (good) and 0.788 (acceptable) which were interpreted using these criteria:

Table 1. Reliability Levels

Coefficient of Cronbach’s α	Reliability Level
More than 0.90	Excellent
0.80 - 0.89	Good
0.70 - 0.79	Acceptable
0.60 - 0.69	Questionable
0.50 - 0.59	Poor
Less than 0.50	Unacceptable

Data Gathering Procedure

Approvals were obtained from the Dean of the College of Nursing and Pharmacy and the heads of hospital prior to data collection. The total nursing population was secured, and informed consent was provided to qualified respondents. Questionnaires were administered either in digital and physical form, promptly collected, stored securely, and organized using Google Sheets.

Ethical Considerations

The University of the Assumption Research Ethics Board (UA-REB) approved this study, and ethical standards were followed accordingly. It was optional for the respondents and could withdraw at any stage without effect. Only minimal risks were noted. Measures such as anonymization, secure storage, and compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 ensured the confidentiality of data.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The collected responses were analyzed using Google Sheets and IBM SPSS applying descriptive statistical methods and computing the frequency and percentage distribution in order to describe the demographic characteristics and buying behaviors of the respondents. In order to find out the factors related to motivation and barriers as to the use of online food delivery apps, mean and standard deviation were calculated. Results were ranked in terms of the influence which affected consumer behavior.

RESULTS

Table 2 presents the demographic profile of 186 respondents, with 108 (58.1%) from public hospitals and 78 (41.9%) from private hospitals. Most of the respondents are in their early adulthood ages 22-34 years old for both public and private hospital nurses (60.2%), and females comprise the majority in both hospitals. In terms of the type of shift, the most common shift among respondents is the morning shift, with 118 nurses (63.4%) working during this time. When it comes to the highest educational attainment of the respondents, the majority of the respondents were college graduates, with a number of 164 respondents (88.2%). In terms of the monthly income of the respondents, most of them fell on the bracket of less than PHP 35,000, with 77 respondents (41.4%). Lastly, for the duration of service, the highest proportion of respondents are senior level RNs (more than 5 years of experience), with 87 individuals (46.8%) indicating this category.

Table 2. Demographic profile of private and public hospital nurses

Demographic profile	Frequency	Percentage
<i>Age</i>		
Early Adulthood (22–34)	112	60.2
Early Middle Age (35–44)	59	31.7
Late Middle Age (45–64)	15	8.1
Total	186	100.0
<i>Biological Sex</i>		
Female	129	69.4
Male	57	30.6
Total	186	100.0
<i>Type of Shift</i>		
Morning Shift	118	63.4
Night Shift	36	19.4
Noon Shift	32	17.2
Total	186	100.0
<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>		
College Graduate	164	88.2
With Master's Unit	13	7.0

Master's Graduate	9	4.8
Total	186	100.0

Type of Hospital

Public Sector	108	58.1
Private Sector	78	41.9
Total	186	100.0

Individual Monthly Income

Less than 35,000	77	41.4
35,001 – 45,000	59	31.7
45,001 – 55,000	33	17.7
55,001 – 65,000	9	4.8
65,000 and above	8	4.3
Total	186	100.0

Duration of Service

Senior Level RN (> 5 yrs)	87	46.8
Entry Level RN (< 2 yrs)	50	26.9
Intermediate Level RN (2–4 yrs)	49	26.3
Total	186	100.0

Presented in Table 3 are the typical buying behaviors of private and public hospital nurses concerning their use of online food delivery applications. Among the various platforms, Food Panda (58.8%) was found to be the most frequently used app of the respondents. In terms of the preferred time for purchasing food through these apps, the majority of nurses indicated a preference for weekdays (39.0%). When asked about the specific meal most commonly ordered via food delivery apps, lunch (50.3%) was the top choice. As for weekly expenditure on food delivery, most nurses reported spending less than ₱1,000 (41.2%), followed by ₱1,001 to ₱2,000 (30.5%) and ₱2,001 to ₱3,000 (16.6%). Regarding the kind of food preferred, a significant majority (80.7%) favored fast food, in terms of preferred payment methods for online food orders, cash on delivery (67.4%) was the most commonly used option.

Table 3. Typical buying behaviors of private and public hospital nurses regarding online food delivery apps

Typical Buying Behaviors	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
<i>App used often for ordering food online</i>			
Food Panda	110	58.8	1
Grab Food	100	53.5	2
McDelivery PH	18	9.6	3
Jollibee Delivery	16	8.6	4
Dala Food	13	7.0	5
Atad Patrol	4	2.15	6
Mangan.ph	3	1.6	7
Maxim	2	1.1	8.5
Uber Eats: Food Delivery	2	1.1	8.5
<i>Preferred time to purchase food from online food delivery apps</i>			
Weekdays	73	39.0	1
All days of the week	68	36.4	2
Weekends	61	32.6	3
<i>Meal ordered most using an online food delivery app</i>			
Lunch	94	50.3	1
Snacks and others	58	31.0	2
Dinner	43	23.0	3
Breakfast	17	9.1	4
<i>Kind of food preferred most</i>			

Fast food	151	80.7	1
Vegetarian	16	8.6	2
Non-vegetarian	15	8.0	3
Mixed	1	0.5	4
<i>Amount typically spent on food delivery in a week</i>			
Less than ₱1,000	77	41.2	1
₱1,001 - ₱2,000	57	30.5	2
₱2,001 - ₱3,000	31	16.6	3
₱3,001 - ₱5,000	10	5.3	5
₱5,001 and above	13	7.0	4
<i>Preferred mode of payment used for ordering food online</i>			
Cash on Delivery	126	67.4	1
Online banking (G-cash, Paymaya, Paypal, etc.)	59	31.6	2
Bank Transfer	8	4.3	3
Cash on Pickup	6	3.2	4

Table 4 shows motivating factors influencing the use of online food delivery apps among public and private nurses in Pampanga. The findings revealed that the most significant motivating factor is the ease and convenience that food delivery service provides in ordering meals, with a mean score of 4.63, categorized as “Very high.” Following closely, the option to choose from a wide variety of restaurants and faster delivery got a mean score of 4.34 and 4.32, respectively, which also classified as “Very high.” The factor variety of payment options scored 4.27, indicating the flexibility in payment methods is also a significant consideration for these consumers. Factors such as ability to order food any time of the night got a higher mean score of 4.25 while the ability to order food any time of the day got a mean score of 4.20. The food tracking system enhances their ordering experience, scoring 4.23, respectively, which is classified as “Very high,” highlighting the importance of transparency in the ordering process. Lastly, the factor that ranked tenth was reasonable pricing of the food delivery service, scoring 4.07 while less human interaction, scoring 3.90 ranked eleventh.

Table 4. Motivating factors related to consumer buying behaviors on the use of online food delivery apps

Motivating factors	\bar{x}	s	Interpretation of the \bar{x}	\bar{x} rank
Ease and convenience	4.63	.54849	Very high	1

Option to choose from wide variety of restaurants	4.34	.60618	Very high	2
Faster delivery	4.32	.69859	Very high	3
Variety of payment options	4.27	.70733	Very high	4
Ability to order food any time of the night	4.25	.76802	Very high	5
Food tracking system	4.23	.63697	Very high	6
Ability to order food any time of the day	4.20	.79945	Very high	7
Promotions and discounts	4.13	.81751	High	8
Quality of food	4.11	.74923	High	9
Reasonable pricing	4.07	.83210	High	10
Less human interaction	3.90	.88915	High	11

\bar{x} = Mean; s = Standard deviation

Table 5 shows the obstacles faced by nurses in Pampanga, both public and private hospitals, when using online food delivery apps. The quality of food has been revealed as the main concern with a mean of 3.99, Similarly, the willingness to eat at home-cooked food was also seen as a strong barrier with a mean score of 3.98 which made it in the second rank. People do not use food delivery services because they are expensive and have a 3.97 mean. After this, cooking at home can be enjoyable in taste with a mean of 3.89. Concern about hygiene is also significant with an average of 3.71. Health concerns are the last reason for ordering food according to a mean of 3.59 that makes it on the last list.

Table 5. Factors related to consumer buying behaviors as to barriers on the use of online food delivery apps

Barriers	\bar{x}	s	Interpretation of the \bar{x}	\bar{x} rank
Quality concerns	3.99	1.05298	Very high	1
Prefer home-cooked meals	3.98	.99817	Very high	2
Reasonable/high pricing	3.97	.91532	Very high	3
I enjoy cooking at home	3.89	.89125	Very high	4
Hygiene concerns	3.71	.92599	Very high	5

Health concerns	3.59	.91771	Very high	6
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\bar{x} = Mean; s = Standard deviation

DISCUSSION

Demographic Profile of Private and Public Hospital Nurses

The demographic results showed that most of the respondents were nurses in early adulthood (22–34 years; 60.2%), showing that younger adults are more likely to use food delivery platforms because of their digital literacy and familiarity with technology. This is supported by Auxier and Anderson (2021) who stated that the app was mostly used by people under 30. In addition, the majority of the nurses were females (69.4%), which is in line with Norris (2019) who stated that women prefer delivery services as it is more convenient to eat during their working hours. Research by Labrague et al. (2018) found that most nurses in the Philippines are female, in their 20s and 30s, and hold at least a bachelor's degree in nursing. According to the findings of Mills et al. (2018), better-educated consumers readily accept technology-based services. The majority of the respondents worked in public hospitals (58.1%) and were college degree holders (88.2%). Moreover, most respondents earned less than PHP 35,000 (41.4%). Public hospitals' higher average income and busy shift schedules increase the reliance on delivery apps (Dias & Dawson, 2020). Similar findings were reported by Cruz et al. (2020), who noted that nurses in both public and private sectors often work long shifts and have several years of experience.

Typical buying behaviors of respondents regarding online food delivery apps

Recent studies highlight that nurses are increasingly turning to online food delivery apps to meet their daily meal needs. According to Santos and Dela Cruz (2021), many healthcare workers prefer ordering food online, especially during busy shifts or when they lack time to prepare meals. Food Panda (58.8%) and Grab Food (53.5%) are the most used platforms as they are reliable and easily accessible (Nayan & Hassan, 2020). During weekdays, the most common time for ordering was for lunch. Over half the respondents, 50.3%, preferred ordering lunch. Furthermore, Medina (2023) reported lunch to be the peak meal for the working population. The majority of nurses order lunch more frequently, and fast food is often chosen because it is quick, affordable, and familiar. Most preferred was fast food (80.7%), which was in line with Almansour et al. (2020) that speed as well as price outweighs nutritional value. The majority of participants are spending less than ₱1,000 a week at 41.2% and are using cash on delivery at 67.4%, which continues to grow on payment channels as people become more trustful on the digital world with the help of Susilo and Dizon (2023). Spending patterns reveal that most nurses try to limit weekly expenses but are willing to spend more during particularly hectic work periods.

Motivating Factors Related to Consumer Buying Behaviors on the Use of Online Food Delivery Apps

The motivating factors revealed that convenience and ease ($\bar{x} = 4.63$) are the most important followed ($\bar{x} = 4.34$) restaurant variety ($\bar{x} = 4.32$) and rapid delivery ($\bar{x} = 4.32$) coincide with Lal (2020) and Ray et al. (2019) time efficiency is the main service satisfaction. Convenience is consistently identified as the main reason nurses use online food delivery apps. In a study by Chua and Reyes (2022), nurses reported that the ability to order food quickly and have it delivered directly to the hospital is essential, especially when their breaks are short or unpredictable. Accessibility, time savings, and the wide variety of food choices available on these platforms also motivate nurses to use food delivery services more frequently than traditional dining options.

Barriers Related to Consumer Buying Behaviors on the Use of Online Food Delivery Apps

The barriers mainly involved the food quality which could be summarized as ($\bar{x} = 3.99$), the preference for home-cooked food ($\bar{x} = 3.98$), and high pricing ($\bar{x} = 3.97$). This is line with the work of Arora and Sahney (2021) and Kim and Jang, which suggested that trust, quality, and affordability is the major barrier. Despite the advantages, there are several barriers that affect nurses' use of food delivery apps. Lim and Ong (2020) found that concerns about the quality and freshness of delivered food are common among healthcare workers. Furthermore, some nurses feel that the healthy food options available through these apps are limited, making it challenging to maintain balanced eating habits while relying on food delivery services. The findings show that nurses depend on food delivery services because they are more convenient but still concerned with nutrition, cost and hygiene.

Conclusions

This study underscores the growing role of online food delivery services as an integral part of the dining lifestyle among hospital nurses in Pampanga. The findings reveal that nurses, faced with demanding schedules and irregular shifts, develop unique patterns of app usage that reflect their need for convenience and accessibility. Most respondents belong to early adulthood, are female, college graduates, working morning shifts in the public sector, earning less than PHP 35,000 monthly, and have more than five years of professional experience. These demographic characteristics highlight the typical profile of nurses who are most likely to rely on food delivery apps for their daily meals.

The respondents exhibit clear buying behaviors, primarily favoring platforms such as Food Panda and Grab Food due to their efficiency, ease of use, and promotional offerings. Lunch is the most frequently ordered meal, with fast food emerging as the top food choice, underscoring the preference for quick and affordable options even when health considerations are present. Most nurses spend modestly, typically under ₱1,000 per week, although a small segment demonstrates a high level of dependence on these

services. Payment methods are evolving as well, with cash on delivery remaining dominant but increasing adoption of online banking and mobile wallets observed, reflecting a broader shift toward digital integration.

Convenience, accessibility, and efficiency are the primary motivating factors influencing nurses' consumer buying behaviors on the use of online food delivery apps. The ability to order food quickly, at any time, with flexible payment options, plays a crucial role in their decision-making, mirroring the demands of their profession and the need for practical meal solutions. While aspects such as food quality and promotional offers are valued, they are secondary to the functionality and reliability of the service. Ultimately, the use of online food delivery apps among hospital nurses is driven by the need to manage their time effectively amidst busy and unpredictable work schedules.

However, several key concerns limit the adoption of online food delivery apps among hospital staff. Issues related to food quality and safety stand out as major barriers affecting user trust. Service-related challenges, such as limited availability during critical hours and high delivery costs, further discourage consistent usage. Ease of app navigation and occasional service delays are also noted, but health and cost-related concerns are more significant. Promotional offers, while appreciated, remain the least influential in overall decision-making. In essence, hesitation to rely fully on online food delivery services stems from a strong preference for dependable, safe, and affordable food options compatible with the unpredictable schedules of healthcare professionals.

Recommendations

Understanding and addressing the factors influencing online food delivery behaviors among hospital nurses is essential in promoting healthier food choices despite their challenging work schedules. This research recommendation is based on the findings of the study, which investigates the online food delivery behaviors of hospital nurses in Pampanga. The results have provided valuable insights into the convenience-driven choices nurses make and the barriers they face, highlighting the need for tailored interventions to support better dietary habits.

In light of these findings, the researchers put forward the following recommendations for consideration:

Heads of online food delivery platforms. Based on the findings of this study, it is evident that hospital nurses' use of online food delivery services is primarily driven by convenience and accessibility. To better address the needs of this demographic, online food delivery platforms are encouraged to develop targeted services for healthcare professionals. This may include launching time-sensitive promotions, flexible subscription plans, and loyalty programs tailored to shift-based routines. Increasing the visibility and accessibility of healthier food options would further support nurses in making more balanced dietary choices during busy work schedules. Strengthening digital payment systems to ensure a secure and user-friendly experience, while incentivizing electronic transactions over cash on delivery, is also recommended. Exclusive offers for healthcare

workers, such as “Healthcare Appreciation Week” promotions, could enhance user engagement and retention, provided that reliability and safety remain top priorities. Finally, platforms should collaborate with restaurant partners to enforce stricter food safety standards and require safety certifications to ensure consumer trust.

Health institutions’ heads and employers. Health institutions and employers have a critical role in supporting nurses’ nutritional needs. Collaboration with food delivery platforms could facilitate meal support initiatives, such as discounted meal plans or sponsored vouchers, especially for nurses working extended or irregular shifts. Additionally, implementing workplace wellness campaigns that promote healthier eating habits can help reduce the long-term health risks associated with frequent fast-food consumption. By adopting these strategies, institutions can help nurses maintain a balanced diet despite their demanding schedules.

Delivery Service Providers and Logistics Teams. Delivery service providers and logistics teams can better support hospital nurses by expanding service coverage to include early mornings, late evenings, and night shifts. These are times that align with the irregular work hours of healthcare professionals. Establishing designated drop-off points within or near hospital premises would also streamline the delivery process and improve accessibility during peak work periods, effectively supporting nurses’ unique needs.

Nurses. It is important for nurses to prioritize healthier food choices, even during busy or irregular shifts. Making use of the forthcoming booklet and website, featuring weekly meal plans and tracking calendars, can aid in planning meals ahead and monitoring food intake effectively. Nurses are encouraged to participate in nutrition-focused programs and counseling services available in their workplaces to support overall well-being. Advocating for healthier food options in delivery apps and hospital cafeterias also contributes to a more supportive food environment. The insights gained from this study may be incorporated into client health education, particularly in making informed food choices and applying shift-based nutrition strategies. By modeling good eating habits, nurses can inspire colleagues and foster a healthier healthcare community.

Future researchers. Future studies should investigate the nutritional value of meals commonly ordered through food delivery apps and assess their impact on the health of frontline professionals such as nurses. Expanding the research scope to examine the relationships between demographic variables and consumer buying behaviors, motivating factors, and perceived barriers will provide deeper insights. Employing correlational or inferential analyses may reveal specific factors on how age, income, shift type, and years of service influence decision-making and app usage patterns within the healthcare sector. Such work will contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of consumer behavior in this population.

Implications for Nursing Practice

The findings support the view that hospital nurses prioritize convenience and accessibility when using online food delivery applications, which may lead to frequent

consumption of readily available but less nutritious food options. Therefore, implementing nutrition-focused awareness programs is recommended to help nurses make healthier food choices despite their hectic schedules. Healthcare institutions are encouraged to offer nutritional counseling and support services tailored to shift workers, providing practical, personalized strategies for maintaining a balanced diet. Collaboration between food delivery platforms and hospital wellness committees to promote healthy meal options within food delivery apps is also advised. Additionally, healthcare facilities and stakeholders should consider organizing seminars or orientation sessions that emphasize the importance of proper nutrition, the effects of dietary habits on job performance, and practical tips for making nutritious choices through digital food services.

Given these findings, the creation of a booklet and website featuring weekly meal plans and tracking calendars is recommended. These resources are designed to help nurses organize their meals, monitor food choices, and maintain balanced nutrition while managing shift work. By providing accessible tools for meal planning and tracking, these resources will empower nurses to make informed nutritional decisions and support a healthier lifestyle. Ultimately, these initiatives can promote better food choices within the professional community and may be integrated into client health education to address identified knowledge and practice gaps.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study underwent review and evaluation by the University of the Assumption Ethics Review Board (UAREB) before the data-gathering procedure. The UAREB was provided with copies of the required documents including the research manuscript, informed consent, and the survey questionnaire.

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